

Kinetics of Growth of Anodic Oxide Films on Titanium in Mixed Solutions of Aqueous Electrolytes and Diethylene Glycol

K. C. KALRA*, K. C. SINGH and MOHINDER SINGH
Chemistry Department, Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak-124 001

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In most of the mechanisms on the growth of anodic oxide films, ionic conduction either within the film and at the interface is assumed to be the rate-controlling step^{1,2}. The results obtained by different workers are at variance and hence further investigation in this area is needed. The growth kinetics and breakdown characteristics of aqueous anodic oxide films on tantalum³ and aluminium⁴ have been reported recently by the authors. In this paper, steady state kinetic data for anodic growth of films on titanium in mixed solutions (3 : 1 by volume) of 100 mol m⁻³ aqueous orthophosphoric acid + diethylene glycol (DEG), 100 mol m⁻³ aqueous sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate + DEG and 100 mol m⁻³ aqueous disodium hydrogen orthophosphate + DEG, at different temperatures and varying current densities have been obtained. The behaviour of Tafel slope and critical assessment of ionic conduction theories with special reference to Dignam's approach⁵ has been presented.

Results and Discussion

Experimental observation for the formation of anodic oxide films on titanium in H₃PO₄ + DEG, Na₂H₂PO₄.2H₂O + DEG and Na₂HPO₄ + DEG were recorded at three different temperatures 293, 308 and 323 K and at various current densities 45, 75, 95 and 165 A m⁻². The variations in formation voltage with time during which charge was passed at different current

densities in NaH₂PO₄.2H₂O + DEG at 293 K are plotted in Fig 1. Similar plots were obtained at other temperatures using H₃PO₄ + DEG and

Fig 1. Variation of voltage of formation with time at 293 K at different current densities : (1) 45, (2) 75, (3) 95 and (4) 165 A m⁻² in mixed solution (3 : 1 by vol) of 100 mol m⁻³ aqueous NaH₂PO₄.2H₂O + diethylene glycol.

Na₂HPO₄ + DEG. The plots were found to be linear upto a film formation voltage of 120 V and become concave towards the time axis at higher formation voltages. The linearity of the plots upto film formation voltage (120 V) showed the field strength to be independent

of film thickness. At higher film formation voltages (> 120 V), the dependence of field strength on film thickness was observed. During the growth of the oxide film in $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ + DEG, the colour changed for every 45–50 V of film formation. For instance, the colour of the film was violet-indigo upto film formation voltage of 50 V, then changed to blue and green upto 100 V. The colour of the oxide film changed from light yellow to deep yellow when the formation voltage was beyond 100 V and this continued upto formation voltage of 150 V. The colour of the film became light red and then deep red when the film formation voltage was greater than 150 V. At the breakdown stage the colour was grey and the specimen became rough. Similar trends were obtained when films were formed in H_3PO_4 + DEG and Na_2HPO_4 + DEG.

The plots of average field strength E against $1/T$ (where T is temperature) at different current densities (Fig. 2) are linear and parallel and have the slope $\delta E/\delta(1/T)$. The Tafel slope $\delta E/\delta \log i$ (where i is the current density) is independent of temperature (Fig. 3), indicating the non-ap-

Fig 2 Plots of E vs $1/T$ in mixed solution (3 : 1 by vol) of 100 mol m^{-3} aqueous $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ + diethylene glycol : (1) 45, (2) 75, (3) 95 and (4) 165 A m^{-2} .

Fig. 3. Field variation with \log (ionic current density) at different temperature : (1) 323, (2) 308 and (3) 293 K in mixed solution (3 : 1 by vol) of 100 mol m^{-3} aqueous $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ + diethylene glycol.

plicability of the single-barrier theory of Cabrera and Mott⁶ since, according to this theory, Tafel slope should be proportional to the temperature. Guntherschulze and Betz⁷ represented the relation between the average field E and i by the equation,

$$i = A \exp (BE) \quad (1)$$

where A and B are constants. The validity of this equation was verified at various current densities and for different aqueous electrolytes. The constants A and B were determined by the method of least-squares at various temperatures and are reported in Table 1. The values of B are found to be temperature-independent. This also implies the non-dependence of Tafel slope on the temperature. The values of B , however, vary with the composition of electrolyte. In each aqueous electrolyte, the value of A increases with an increase in temperature. The increase in the value of A with temperature may be due to an increase in the number of active sites, i.e. the number of mobile ions at the metal surface. The values of A were also found to depend on the composition of the electrolyte.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF THE GUNTHERSCHULZE-BETZ CONSTANTS A AND B AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES FOR MIXED SOLUTIONS (3 : 1 BY VOL) OF 100 mol m⁻³ AQUEOUS ELECTROLYTE + DIETHYLENE GLYCOL

Aqueous electrolyte	Temp K	A $\times 10^2 \text{ Am}^{-2}$	B $\times 10^{-8} \text{ mV}^{-1}$
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	293	0.047	0.324
	308	0.089	0.323
	323	0.167	0.321
H ₃ PO ₄	293	0.073	0.281
	308	0.126	0.282
	323	0.220	0.284
Na ₂ HPO ₄	293	0.055	0.310
	308	0.098	0.310
	323	0.176	0.309

Young⁸ observed a field-dependent Tafel slope $\delta E/\delta \ln i$ and this dependence was accounted by the equation,

$$i = i_0 \exp \{-(Q - \alpha E + \gamma E^2)/KT\} \quad (2)$$

where Q , α and γ are all positive constants and K is Boltzmann constant. Dignam⁵ justified the quadratic variation in field with ionic current density in explaining the field and temperature dependence of Tafel slopes. According to him at high fields the relation between ionic current density and field strength is

$$i = i_0 \exp [-\{\phi - \mu^* E(1 - \mu^* E/C\phi)\}/KT] \quad (3)$$

where i_0 is the primary current density, ϕ the zero-field activation energy, C a dimensionless quantity and μ^* the zero-field activation dipole. Comparing equations (2) and (3) we have $\phi = Q$, $\mu^* = \alpha$ and $C = \alpha^2/\gamma Q$.

Furthermore, equation (3) may be written as

$$E = \frac{\phi C}{2\mu^*} \left[1 - \left\{ 1 - \frac{4}{C} - \frac{4KT}{C\phi} \ln \left(\frac{i}{i_0} \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \quad (4)$$

Since the plot of E vs $1/T$ is linear, then equation (4) may be written as

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial(1/T)} = S = -\frac{KT^2}{\mu^*} \ln \left(\frac{i}{i_0} \right) / \left\{ 1 - \frac{4}{C} - \frac{4KT}{C\phi} \ln \left(\frac{i}{i_0} \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (5)$$

If $\delta S/\delta \ln i = 0$, i.e. the Tafel slope is independent of temperature, we have from equation (5),

$$C = 4 + \frac{2KT}{\phi} \ln \left(\frac{i}{i_0} \right) \quad (6)$$

The reciprocal of the Tafel slope is given by

$$B = \frac{\partial \ln i}{\partial E} = \mu^* \left(1 - \frac{2\mu^* E}{C\phi} \right) / KT \quad (7)$$

The parameters μ^* , $\mu^* E/C\phi$ and C can be computed using the above equations; we have

$$\mu^* = \left(1 + \frac{TE}{S} \right) KTB \quad (8)$$

$$\text{where, } B = \frac{\delta \ln i}{\delta E}$$

$$\frac{\mu^* E}{C\phi} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{S}{TE} \right)^{-1} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{and } C = 4 \left[1 + \left\{ \frac{1}{1 + \frac{TE}{S}} \right\}^2 \right]^{-1} \quad (10)$$

Above equations are based on the assumption that μ^* , ϕ and C are temperature-independent quantities. The linear curves are parallel (Fig. 3), i.e. $\delta S/\delta \ln i = 0$. Values of μ^* , ϕ and C were calculated at various current densities as functions of temperature from equations (8)–(10) in the presence of H₃PO₄, NaH₂PO₄·2H₂O and Na₂HPO₄, and the data together with the mean values of E are recorded in Table 2. The equation of ionic conduction can also be written as

$$i = i_0 \exp \left\{ - \left[\phi - W^* E \left\{ 1 - \ln \left(\frac{W^* E}{2\phi} \right) - \frac{W^* E}{2\phi} \right\} \right] / KT \right\} \quad (11)$$

where W^* is the Morse function parameter (and has the same dimensions as μ^*), and the values were calculated using equation (12),

$$W^* = \left[\left\{ 1 + \frac{2}{C} \left(\frac{\mu^* E}{\phi} \right)^2 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} - 1 \right] \frac{\phi}{E} \quad (12)$$

TABLE 2—VALUES OF E (EXPERIMENTAL) μ^* , C , ϕ , W^* , $W[E]$ AND $\log i_0$ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND CURRENT DENSITIES USING THE DIGNAM EQUATION FOR MIXED SOLUTION (3 : 1 BY VOL.) OF 100 mol m^{-3} AQUEOUS ELECTROLYTE + DIETHYLENE GLYCOL

Aqueous electrolyte	Temp K	E mV m^{-1}	$m^* \times 10^{10}$ em	C	$\phi \times 10^{19}$ J	$W^* \times 10^{10}$ em	$W[E] \times 10^{19}$ J	$\log i_0$
Current density : 45 A m^{-2}								
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	293	695	0.946	2.29	0.678	0.064	0.580	7.880
	308	502	0.959	2.22	0.653	0.051	0.580	7.577
	323	310	0.962	2.15	0.621	0.034	0.575	7.252
H ₃ PO ₄	308	448	0.823	2.19	0.598	0.037	0.542	7.189
Na ₂ HPO ₄	308	495	0.921	2.22	0.619	0.049	0.550	7.270
Current density : 75 A m^{-2}								
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	293	852	0.975	2.35	0.702	0.078	0.580	8.102
	308	662	0.992	2.29	0.677	0.076	0.579	7.788
	323	470	0.998	2.22	0.647	0.052	0.576	7.485
H ₃ PO ₄	308	638	0.854	2.26	0.625	0.053	0.543	7.421
Na ₂ HPO ₄	308	652	0.952	2.29	0.641	0.064	0.548	7.472
Current density : 95 A m^{-2}								
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	293	925	0.989	2.38	0.713	0.085	0.579	8.194
	308	727	1.005	2.32	0.686	0.074	0.578	7.881
	323	540	1.014	2.25	0.658	0.060	0.575	7.577
H ₃ PO ₄	308	712	0.866	2.29	0.634	0.059	0.542	7.513
Na ₂ HPO ₄	308	740	0.969	2.33	0.653	0.073	0.547	7.564
Current density : 165 A m^{-2}								
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	293	1095	1.020	2.44	0.740	0.100	0.579	8.433
	308	905	1.041	2.38	0.718	0.091	0.580	8.141
	323	716	1.053	2.33	0.686	0.079	0.574	7.807
H ₃ PO ₄	308	910	0.899	2.36	0.663	0.075	0.543	7.763
Na ₂ HPO ₄	308	912	1.003	2.39	0.682	0.089	0.549	7.824

The values for the net activation energy $W[E]$ were calculated using equation (13),

$$W[E] = \phi - \mu^* E (1 - \mu^* E / C\phi) \quad (13)$$

and are reported in Table 2. From equations (3) and (13),

$$i_0 = i \exp \{W[E]/KT\}$$

The values of i_0 are recorded in Table 2. It is found that the parameter μ^* , W^* , i_0 , ϕ and C are dependent upon temperature, current density and the nature of the electrolyte. Dignam⁵ did not observe the dependence of these parameters because of the non-availability of steady state data for a wide range of current density, temperature and composition of the electrolyte. The values of $W[E]$ are independent of the current

density and temperature but vary with the composition of the electrolyte. The quantity $\mu^* E / C\phi$ (in eqn. 3) measures the extent of the contribution of the quadratic term over the entire range of data and was found to be (2.74–9.48%), (3.58–10.38%) and (3.54–10.06%) for H₃PO₄, NaH₂PO₄·2H₂O and Na₂HPO₄ respectively.

It appears that increase in temperature causes increase in activation distance from the mean position and hence increases charge-activation distance product (μ^*). $W[E]$ is net activation energy, therefore, should not be affected by temperature and current density, and our results substantiate this. The increase in the values of μ^* with current density may be due to increased charge. The number of mobile ions (and also the magnitude of charge) will vary in different aqueous media and this will vary the magnitude μ^* .

Experimental

Square titanium specimens (2 cm²) with short tags were cut from a sheet of titanium (99.9% purity). The edges of specimens were abraded with fine emery paper. The specimens were washed with distilled water. The specimens were polished by dipping them in a freshly prepared mixture of 70% HNO₃ + 98% H₂SO₄ + 40% HF + H₂O (2 : 1 : 1 : 1 by volume) for 3–4 s, then washed with distilled water and dried in a current of hot air. The entire process was repeated again.

Titanium specimens prepared by the above method were anodised in a glass cell having the large platinum wire gauze which served as a cathode. The position of the specimen was set concentric to the central axis of the cathode. The cell was immersed in a controlled temperature bath (± 0.5 K) in the temperature range 293–308 K. Anodic polarisation of titanium was carried out at constant current using a constant current generator (General Electronics, India) designed specially for the purpose. The supply of current was cut off by an electronic control after the desired voltage of film formation was reached. Before anodisation, a thick anodic oxide film on the tags of the specimens were made in their own electrolyte solutions so that formation of oxide layer took place only at the working area of the specimens. Different formation voltages (10–180 V) were used for kinetic studies and for calculating the thickness and field strength of the oxide films. The oxide films for these studies were formed in aqueous H₃PO₄ + DEG (C₄H₁₀O₃), aqueous NaH₂PO₄·2H₂O + DEG and aqueous Na₂HPO₄ + DEG.

The time for the passage of current for forming film through successive intervals of voltage was recorded. The electrolytes used for the formation of anodic oxide films were of analytical

grade (Aldrich). Thickness of the film was determined through Faraday's law. When the current efficiency is unity, the thickness is given by $MQ/4\rho FA$, where M is the gram molecular weight of the TiO₂ film, Q the charge, ρ the density of the titanium oxide film, F the Faraday constant and A the area of specimen. The value of the factor $M/4\rho FA$ was found to be $2.69898 \times 10^{-7} \text{ C}^{-1}\text{m}$. The density of TiO₂ films was taken as 3480 kg m⁻³ as reported by Mizushima¹. The field E at any given current density, was determined using the values of the calculated thickness and the corresponding voltage of formation.

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